

Comparative Evaluation of IBA CC01 and CC04 Ionization Chambers for Small-Field Dosimetry

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Abstrat:

Accurate small-field dosimetry is critical for the precision of stereotactic radiotherapy treatments (SRS/SBRT), but it remains challenging due to steep dose gradients and the loss of charged-particle equilibrium. This study aims to compare the performance of two ionization chambers with different sensitive volumes, the IBA CC01 (0.01 cm³) and CC04 (0.04 cm³), for small-field measurements on an Elekta Versa HD linear accelerator.

Percent depth dose (PDD) curves, lateral beam profiles, and relative output factors were measured in water at an SSD of 90 cm for 6 MV FFF and 10 MV FFF photon beams. Field sizes ranged from 1×1 cm² to 5×5 cm², with 10×10 cm² used as the reference field. Measurements were performed at depths of 1.6, 3, 5, and 10 cm. The results were compared with Elekta Golden Beam Data (GBD) using a gamma analysis with a 2%/2 mm criterion.

Both chambers showed excellent agreement with the reference data, achieving gamma pass rates greater than 99% and output factor differences ≤ 2%. The responses of the CC01 and CC04 were generally very similar; the observed differences were limited and mainly attributable to volume-averaging effects. The CC01 provided slightly better spatial resolution for the smallest fields, whereas the CC04 remained reliable for fields ≥ 1 cm according to the 2%/2 mm criterion.

These results confirm that both CC01 and CC04 chambers provide accurate and robust small-field dosimetry for 6 MV FFF and 10 MV FFF beams. Their strong agreement with Golden Beam Data supports their use in commissioning and quality assurance of stereotactic radiotherapy treatments.

Keywords:

Small-field dosimetry; Ionization chamber; FFF beams; Golden Beam Data; CC01; CC04.